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Auditing quality in qualitative research

Symposium - Open science in qualitative research

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Tutorial audit trailing

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How can Open Science be applied in Qualitative Research?

How can we open up rigor in qualitative research?

Open science @Edubron

Open science @Edubron

Auditing quality in qualitative research

Essential concepts in Open Qualitative Research

INTERPRETATIVE

ITERATIVE

- **Reproducibility – Transparency – Traceability – Accountability - Auditability**
- **Reflexivity**
- **Positionality**

Essential concepts in Open Qualitative Research

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- **Reflexivity**
- **Positionality**

ELSEVIER

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Learning and Instruction

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/learninstruc

Unraveling low-educated adults' motivation for second-chance education: A multidimensional perspective

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pose. The procedure used was approved by the Ethics Committee for the Social Sciences and Humanity (SHW_21_56). The methodology of this study is accompanied by an extensive audit trail made available on Open Science Framework (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/DTKXG>), providing more details on the reflections and methodological choices made throughout the research process, strengthening the quality of this study (Akkerman et al., 2008; Carcary, 2009) (Appendix A).

<https://osf.io/dtkxg/>

Introduction

The purpose of this audit trail is threefold. Firstly, we aim to be **transparent** about the **methodological and theoretical choices** that were made to enhance trustworthiness. Secondly, we want to articulate **the quality checks** performed in this qualitative study to enhance validity and reliability of the study. Finally, we aim to ground these choices and quality checks in the scientific literature. By being transparent about the research process, **the authors are made accountable** for the choices made, and it also enables **other researchers to follow the decision trail** to achieve comparable conclusions, given the data, the researchers' perspectives, and situation (e.g., Akkerman et al., 2006; Carcary, 2009; Koch, 2006; Olmos-Vega, 2023; Sandelowski, 1986).

Making explicit the decisions made throughout the process, **we acknowledge that qualitative research is interpretive and subjective** in nature and therefore follow Walsham's (2006, pp. 321) statement *"that we are **biased** by our background, knowledge, and predispositions to see things in a certain way and others not"*. We therefore open the audit trail with a **positionality statement** of the researchers

Audit trail reading guide

The purpose of an audit trail is to guide an external auditor through the various decisions made throughout the research process. These choices can be theoretical, methodological, or analytical in nature. Additionally, an audit trail aims to provide insight into the researchers' reflections (Olmos-Vega, 2023). In line with Carcary (2009), an audit trail thus has a physical aspect (theoretical and methodological choices) and an intellectual aspect. The intellectual aspect of an audit trail encompasses the researchers' reflections that lead to certain theoretical and methodological decisions. Furthermore, these reflections also determine what is considered critical and therefore should be focused on in each of the research phases. Based on this logic, we adopt the following structuring within the audit trail (Table 1).

Table 1

Audit trail reading guide

Physical audit trail		
A.	Theory	What decisions are made regarding theory?
B.	Research objectives	What decisions are made regarding research objectives and research questions?
C.	Participants	What decisions are made regarding sample?
D.	Instruments	What decisions are made regarding instruments?
E.	Analysis	What decisions are made regarding analysis?
Intellectual audit trail		
i.	Critical aspect	Which aspects do the researchers consider as critical in a specific phase?
ii.	Reflections	What are reflections regarding the critical aspect?

Auditability

=

**Evaluation of rigor in qualitative
research**

Reflexive rigor

Reflexivity on positionality

Reflexive rigor → Theory

To unravel the concept of 'motivation', multiple theoretical perspectives might be warranted. At this point we want to explore relevant theoretical frameworks that might be helpful in understanding motivation of SCE-learners, rather than to use a specific set of theoretical frameworks a priori.

Guiding theoretical frameworks at this point:

- **Self-determination theory** (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2000; 2017; 2020) to assess quality of motivation.
- **Aspirations-achievement paradox** (Mickelson, 1990) to assess the multidimensional nature of the construct of 'motivation' in SCE.
- **Multidimensional model of 'motivation'** found by Carré (2001) to assess the

Reflexive rigor → Theory

- To ensure that participants have ample opportunity to express themselves and **shape their own motivational narrative** during the interviews, we choose to inquire with sufficient openness into the two expected dimensions, namely 'participation motivation' and 'achievement motivation', but **without using any other a priori theoretical underpinning** within both dimensions.

A. Theory

- **We expect** at this point two dimensions: 'participation motivations' VERSUS 'learning motivation'.
 - Multidimensional model (Carré, 2001)
 - Aspirations-achievement paradox (Mickelson, 1990)
- **We expect** that motives will differ in quality.
 - Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2000; 2017; 2020)

Reflexive rigor → Theory

Interaction theory and analysis:

- To leave sufficient openness to the context-specific uniqueness of the concept of motivation, we adopt an approach that will not a priori distort the conclusions to be drawn by using fixed theoretical lenses. Of course, it is clear at this stage that motivational psychology frameworks will be used, as the research team has most experience with these frameworks. Which frameworks are then needed to properly understand the various dimensions of motivation, is still open currently.
- The goal is first to see what possible dimensions of motivation are present in the data to then compile an appropriate theoretical framework. We expect two main
 - **Positionality authors 1, 3, 4 and external member 2:** Coding is always done from the frame of reference of the respective researcher(s) (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Walsham's, 2006, pp.

Reflexive rigor → Theory

The result of phase 4 shows that the SDT-framework and associated mini-theories are suitable for describing the dimensionality mainly within participation motivation. These theories however, are insufficient for an adequate description of learning motivation.

Reflexive rigor → Theory

A. Theory

- **We expect** at this point two dimensions: 'participation motivation' VERSUS 'learning motivation', based on following theoretical frameworks:
 - Multidimensional model (Carré, 2000)
 - Aspirations-achievement paradox (Mickelson, 1990)

Reflexive rigor → Theory

A. Theory

- **We expect** that motives will differ in quality (SDT (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2000; 2017; 2020)). The assessment of 'quality' will provide an additional set of subdimensions within 'participation motivation' and 'learning motivation'. Following mini-theories within SDT are used to distinguish further motivational subdimensions.
 - Goal Content Theory (GCT) to assess the quality of the life goals pursued by participating in SCE ('what' of motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2017)).
We expect following theoretical codes:
 - Extrinsic goals
 - Image
 - Money
 - Social recognition
 - Intrinsic goals
 - Meaningful relationships
 - Personal growth
 - Contribution to society
 - SDT-continuum to assess the quality of the internalization of each of the goals ('why' of motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2000)).
We expect following codes based on this theory:
 - Internal regulation
 - Identified regulation
 - Introjected regulation
 - Approaching
 - Avoiding

Reflexiv

A. Theory

- **We expect** at this point two dimensions: 'participation motivations' VERSUS 'learning motivation'
 - Multidimensional model (Carré, 2000)
 - Aspirations-achievement paradox (Mickelson, 1990)
- Within 'participation motivation' **we expect**:
 - GCT to assess the quality of the life goals pursued by participating in SCE ('what' of motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2017)). **We expect** following dimensions. A part of the theoretically expected codes cover participation goals present in the interview data and some of the data-driven codes might be fitted into the theoretical distinction between:
 - Extrinsic goals
 - Intrinsic goals
 - SDT-continuum to assess the quality of the internalization of each of the goals ('why' of motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2000; 2017; 2020)). **We expect** following dimensions:
 - Intrinsic regulation
 - Identified regulation
 - Introjected regulation
 - Approaching
 - Avoiding
 - External regulation
 - Approaching
 - Avoiding
 - Amotivation
- Learning motivation:
 - Achievement Goal Theory (AGT) to distinguish 'goals' (what?) (Elliot, 1999; Elliot & McGregor, 2001) from the reasons underlying these goals (why?) (SDT). **We expect** following dimensions:
 - Mastery-approaching goals

Reflexive rigor → Theory

H1: Intrinsic and extrinsic goals with subdimensions can be distinguished. (GCT (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Kasser & Ryan, 1993, 1996; Ryan & Deci, 2017; Vansteenkiste et al., 2014)) (Research objective 1)

H2: We expect a relationship between the quality of the goal pursued and the internalization of that specific goal. We expect in other words that goals can be placed on the SDT-continuum and that (H2a) different regulation types are present; (H2b) For 'Introjected regulation' and 'External regulation', we may also expect a further subdivision into 'approaching' and 'avoiding'. (GCT (Ryan & Deci, 2017; Vansteenkiste et al., 2014); SDT (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2000; 2017; 2020)) (Research objective 1 and 2). We also expect that (H2c) Intrinsic goals are more often associated with good-quality internalization; (H2d) extrinsic goals are more often associated with poor-quality internalization. (Research objective 2). We also expect that (H2e) Participation 'goals' and 'internalization' are 2 separate dimensions, so there is not everywhere a one to one association between the goal and the internalization of the goal (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2017; Sheldon et al., 2004; Vansteenkiste et al., 2014). (Research objective 2)

H3: Based on person-oriented studies, we expect that individuals cannot be characterized by merely one dimension of motivation, but do have unique combinations of motives. We therefore expect that 'types' of participants can be distinguished based on the quality of goals pursued and internalization. Based on previous person-centered SDT research, we expect 4 profiles (Vansteenkiste et al., 2009) (Research objective 2):

- Good-quality motivational profile
- Poor-quality motivational profile
- High-quantity motivational profile
- Low-quantity motivational profile

Reflexive rigor → Research objectives

- **Positionality author 1:** With these items, we attempted to measure the concept of 'achievement motivation' ['learning motivation' in the manuscript]. This high-quality motivation to engage in learning behavior does not align with how author 1 has observed motivation in the classroom.

Reflexive rigor → Research objectives

- **Research objective 1:** Unraveling the dimensionality of motivation among SCE-learners. (We expect at least 2 dimensions: ‘participation motivation’ versus ‘achievement motivation’)
- **Research objective 2:** Exploring the relationship between the dimensions of motivation among SCE-learners.

Reflexive rigor → Research objectives

The two initial research objectives are reformulated into four more specific research objectives:

- **Research objective 1:** Unraveling the dimensionality of motivation among SCE-learners.
We use four theoretical dimensions:
 - 'Participation motivation'
 - 'Goals' (GCT)
 - 'Internalization' (SDT-continuum)
 - 'Learning motivation'
 - 'Goals' (AGT)
 - 'Internalization' (SDT-continuum)
- **Research objective 2:** Exploring variable-oriented associations between 'goals' and 'internalization'.
 - To assess the quality of each of the identified goals and to identify the strongest relationships for the emerging theory.
- **Research objective 3:** Exploring person-oriented associations between codes.
 - To identify profiles of participants being distinct in their participation and learning motivation. Specific patterns of motivational subdimensions, might provide 'key dimensions' of motivation.
- **Research objective 4:** Providing a contextualized conceptualization of 'motivation' for the specific population of SCE-learners.
 - Based on the theoretical frameworks used in this study, this emerging theory should

Reflexive rigor → Participants

- **Positionality author 1:**

- Since author 1 has a network in SCE and can more easily get pass 'gatekeepers' (Cohen et al., 2018), a different sampling strategy is chosen. Author 1 is present during various class sessions where the questionnaire is completed. Based on scores on various motivation scales, potential participants who may vary in their motivation profile are orally invited for an interview on that same day (of filling in the questionnaire). Author 1 also clarifies the ethical aspects of the research to create an atmosphere of trust (Cohen et al., 2018).

Reflexive rigor → Instrument

- **Positionality author 1:**

- To conduct the interviews in a consistent manner, an interview protocol is required (Kvale & Brinkman, 2009) (Appendix A). Interviews require a certain level of metacognitive skills of the participant. It is expected that the lack of this metacognitive capacity in the target population could possibly negatively affect the quality of the data. For that reason, it is advised to use the interview guideline in a flexible way and leave sufficient openness for unsolicited answers (Cohen et al., 2018; Small & Calarco, 2022).
- Due to the first authors' extensive knowledge of the program SCE-learners are enrolled in, as well as their ability to assess the language level of the participants accurately, language and terminology are less likely to be a barrier during the interview. Author 1 also emphasizes their experience as a teacher and guidance counselor at the beginning of the interview, which may contribute to a reduced power imbalance and potentially foster more openness from the participants during the interview (Cohen et al., 2018; Secules et al., 2019).

Methodological rigor

Methodological rigor → Quality “check” of the data

Metacognitive capacity participants. In line with the idea that we should be aware of overinterpretation of unclear text fragments, the 5 remaining interviews also raised the consideration whether the content of the interview was sufficiently interpretable for coding.

- The interview DST2_29 is difficult to code. There is a language barrier and by consequence the participant does not understand the interview questions and gives very short and superficial answers. Wanting to fit extracts of this interview into the codes, would mean an overinterpretation of the data. We decide not to include this interview.

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"A nine, so you feel like you're learning a lot in the program. Can you give an example of that? Like when you feel, 'I'm really learning a lot.' Um... I don't have a specific example right now." [DST2_29]

"Yeah, and does it sometimes happen that you're sitting there during class thinking, 'Hmm, I'm actually not feeling motivated today?'" "Sometimes." "Yeah, and could you tell me about a certain class... where you say..." "No, not really, no." [DST2_29]

"could you describe to me what you had to do at that moment and what the moment was about in English? I don't remember that anymore. Yeah... okay, um... do you remember what the teacher did exactly? Not really... I can't recall.

[DST2_29]

Methodological rigor → Quality “check” of the data

Appendix B

Motivational profile and background characteristics of the participants in the study.

Participant	Motivational profile	Institution	Gender	Age	Country of birth	Educational level mother
Maria	Good-quality	A	Female	39	Other country	> ISCED level III
Jacky*	Good-quality	A	Female	20	Other country	> ISCED level III
Paula	Good-quality	A	Female	18	Country of the study	> ISCED level III
Ray	Good-quality	A	Male	24	Country of the study	> ISCED level III
Yoko	Good-quality	A	Female	33	Other country	< ISCED level III
Siham	Good-quality	A	Female	37	Other country	> ISCED level III
Ada	Good-quality	B	Female	19	Country of the study	> ISCED level III
Henry	High-quantity	A	Male	22	Country of the study	< ISCED level III
Martha	High-quantity	B	Female	18	Other country	< ISCED level III
Lisa	High-quantity	B	Female	20	Country of the study	< ISCED level III
Ahmed	Low-quantity	A	Male	18	Country of the study	> ISCED level III
Luke	Low-quantity	A	Male	18	Other country	> ISCED level III
Guo	Low-quantity	A	Male	18	Country of the study	> ISCED level III
Bob	Low-quantity	B	Male	20	Country of the study	< ISCED level III
Kate	Low-quantity	B	Female	19	Other country	< ISCED level III
Tom	Low-quantity	B	Male	20	Country of the study	< ISCED level III
Rashid	Low-quantity	B	Male	24	Country of the study	> ISCED level III
José	Poor-quality	B	Male	18	Country of the study	> ISCED level III
Peter	Poor-quality	B	Male	19	Other country	< ISCED level III

* Due to considerations of data quality, this interview was omitted from the analysis.

Methodological rigor → Quality “check” coding

- **Positionality author 1:**

- Since author 1 conducted the interviews and as an ‘insider’ is better suited to adequately understand and therefore, interpret the interview data for epistemological and ontological reasons, the effective coding was mainly performed by author 1 (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Secules et al., 2019).
- Since the coding itself is essential to research objective 1 (and is also the basis for the other research objectives), it is important to check the quality of the coding (O’Connor & Joffe, 2020; Patton, 2002) and thus the interpretations made.
 - As a first step, we examine how consistent author 1 is in interpreting the interview data. The aim here is mainly to check whether the different codes are sufficiently distinguishable from each other (mutual exclusivity) (Appendix K).
 - Based on the first step, any adjustments to the coding tree are made and then, in a second step (Phase 8), we investigate whether an independent second coder arrives at similar interpretations and thus coding, given the definitions in the codebook (Appendix L).

- **Reflections peer debriefing after calculation intra-coder reliability:**

Methodological rigor → Quality “check” coding

- **Positionality author 1:**

- Since author 1 conducted the interviews and as an ‘insider’ is better suited to adequately understand and therefore, interpret the interview data, the effective coding was mainly performed by author 1. However, it is also necessary to have the coding work done by a second coder from a critical point of view, who can look at the extracts with more distance. In this way the double coding fuels the peer debriefing: a low Cohen’s kappa gives an insight into the codes that are difficult to distinguish or where overinterpretation of author 1 is possible.
- **Positionality author 2:** In this phase we decide to include ‘author 2’, which has expertise in the theoretical frameworks, as they were also used in previous research by this author (related to adults’ professional learning). Moreover, author 2 has expertise mainly in qualitative research.

- **Reflections peer debriefing after calculation inter-coder reliability:**

Table 1

Dimensions within participation motivation, representation of dimensions among participants (*f* coded interviews) and data (*f* coded extracts), and inter-coder reliability (κ).

Code	Definition	κ	<i>f</i> coded interviews	<i>f</i> coded extracts
Participation motivation – Goals (What?)		0.52	100.00%	48.37%
Extrinsic goals	Goals not satisfying basic psychological needs	0.67	94.44%	17.39%
Diploma as an entrance ticket	Pursuing a diploma serves as an entrance ticket to a job or higher education.	0.53	72.22%	5.43%
Diploma as such	Pursuing a diploma as an end without a clearly stated ulterior motive.	0.84	88.89%	9.51%
Social recognition ^a	Pursuing a diploma because of the recognition of others.	1.00	33.33%	2.45%
Intrinsic goals	Goals satisfying basic psychological needs	0.58	100.00%	30.98%
Feeling better	Participating in SCE because learners will feel better about themselves again in that environment.	0.59	72.22%	11.68%
Meaningful relationships ^a	Participating in SCE because learners expect to have better relationships with peers or teachers in that environment.	0.85	55.56%	4.35%
More freedom/autonomy	Participating in SCE because learners expect to obtain more freedom/autonomy in that environment.	0.38	33.33%	2.99%
Personal growth ^a	Participating in SCE as it contributes to the development of competencies, career, or oneself as a person.	0.68	94.44%	19.29%
Diploma to do what you love	Pursuing a diploma to be able to do (a job) what you love in life.	0.57	77.78%	8.15%
Participation motivation – Internalization of goals (Why?)		0.68	100.00%	51.63%
Intrinsic regulation ^a	Participating in SCE out of pleasure, interest, and fascination.	0.61	72.22%	11.41%
Identified regulation ^a	Participating in SCE out of personal value, usefulness, or meaningfulness.	0.53	83.33%	8.70%
Introjected regulation ^a		0.66	77.78%	7.61%
Approaching ^a	Participating in SCE to obtain pride.	0.77	38.89%	4.08%
Avoiding ^a	Participating in SCE to avoid shame, guilt, or fear.	0.44	50.00%	3.53%
Diploma regulation	Valuing (identified regulation) their participation in SCE for obtaining a diploma that is a prerequisite for a job or higher education (external regulation).	0.93	88.89%	7.61%
Lack of internal regulation	Participating in SCE to obtain a diploma (external regulation), but besides that having no other underlying motivation (non-regulation).	0.80	77.78%	16.30%

Methodological rigor → Quality “check” coding

Saturation of coding (Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Charmaz & Thornberg, 2021). As **principles of grounded theory** are used to code the data and to arrive at a parsimonious context-specific emerging theory, we want to obtain **‘theoretical saturation’**. According to Starks and Trinidad (2007, pp. 1375), theoretical saturation occurs **“when the complete range of constructs that make up the theory is fully represented by the data”**.

- **Coding the 4 remaining interviews** revealed that no additional constructs were present in these interviews.

Methodological rigor → Evolution coding tree / definitions

REFLEXIVE RIGOR

Reflections on theory

Reflections on research objectives

Reflections on participants

Reflections on instrument and data quality

METHODOLOGICAL RIGOR

Data cleaning

Intra- and inter-coder reliability

Saturation

Peer debriefing → impact coding tree

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